

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Role of Random Texture Scattering on the Absorptance Enhancement in Halide Perovskite Layers

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Calculations

Poruba's model [1]:

Complex refractive index N can be defined from refractive index n and absorption coefficient α as follows (i is imaginary unit and λ is wavelength):

$$N = n + i \frac{\alpha \lambda}{4\pi}$$

Fresnel intensity coefficients for perpendicular incidence for reflectance R and transmittance T (n_1 is refractive index of medium on the first, incoming side, n_2 is refractive index of medium on the second, transmitting side) are defined as follows:

$$t_{12} = \frac{2n_1}{n_1 + n_2}, T_{12} = \frac{n_2}{n_1} |t_{12}|^2$$

$$r_{12} = \frac{n_1 - n_2}{n_1 + n_2}, R_{12} = |r_{12}|^2$$

The amount of specularly transmitted or reflected light is obtained by multiplying Fresnel intensity coefficients by scalar scattering theory [2] scattering factors (σ is RMS roughness, n_f is refractive index of film, n_a is the refractive index of ambient, φ is the angle of incidence that for trapped light can be approximated by π/n_f):

$$S_T = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{2\pi(n_f - n_a)\sigma}{\lambda} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$S_{R,0} = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{4\pi n_f \sigma}{\lambda} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$S_R = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{4\pi n_f \sigma \cos \varphi}{\lambda} \right)^2 \right] \cong \exp \left[- \left(\frac{4\pi n_f \sigma \cos(\pi/n_f)}{\lambda} \right)^2 \right]$$

The light absorbed directly without scattering event is (d is the film thickness):

$$A_{dir} = S_T (1 - e^{-\alpha d})$$

Relative portion of photons scattered at the hitting the first surface and at the hitting the surface after reflection from the back side of the film is (indices f and s mean film and substrate, respectively):

$$P_0 = (1 - S_T) + S_T R_{fs} e^{-2\alpha d} R_{fa} (1 - S_{R0})$$

Probability of scattered light escaping through escape cone into substrate, for Lambertian case is:

$$P_{esc} = (n_s/n_f)^2$$

The multiplication factor of average optical path increase for Lambertian distribution. Angles β and γ are the integration limits that are linked to escape cone:

$$Y_\beta^\gamma = \frac{\int_\beta^\gamma \sin \varphi d\varphi}{\int_\beta^\gamma \sin \varphi \cos \varphi d\varphi}$$

Figure S1: Illustration of the different contributions into Poruba model.

The portion of light (scattered and non-scattered) absorbed between first and second scattering event (γ is the angle of escape cone into substrate for which the condition is $\sin(\gamma) = n_s/n_f$):

$$A_1 = (1 - P_{esc})[1 - \exp(-2Y_\gamma^{\pi/2} \alpha d)] + P_{esc}[1 - \exp(-Y_0^\gamma \alpha d)]$$

The relative intensity reduction between the first and second scattering event is:

$$P_1 = (1 - P_{esc}) \exp(-2Y_\gamma^{\pi/2} \alpha d)$$

The portion of light (scattered and non-scattered, inside and outside of escape cone) absorbed between first and second scattering event (γ is the angle of escape cone into substrate for which the condition is $\sin(\gamma) = n_s/n_f$):

$$A_2 = [(1 - P_{esc})(1 - S_r) + S_r][1 - \exp(-2Y_\gamma^{\pi/2} \alpha d)] + P_{esc}(1 - S_r)[1 - \exp(-Y_0^\gamma \alpha d)][1 + R_{fs} \exp(-Y_0^\gamma \alpha d)]$$

The relative intensity reduction between each two consecutive scattering events is (of non-scattered light and light scattered outside escape cone):

$$A_2 = [(1 - P_{esc})(1 - S_r) + S_r] \exp(-2Y_\gamma^{\pi/2} \alpha d)$$

Altogether the intensity of absorbed light is the sum of an infinite row:

$$A = A_{dir} + P_0 A_1 + P_0 P_1 R_{fa} A_2 \frac{1}{1 - P_2}$$

Transparent conductive oxide (TCO) layers preparation

The samples A, B, and C were prepared on Corning glass using RF magnetron sputtering from 2 inch ZnO (99,99%) target with substrate to target distance 35 mm at RF power 75 W, 150 W and 175 W, respectively. Argon pressure was 2×10^{-2} Pa. Without any additional intentional heating the substrate temperature was approximately 100 °C. Deposition time was 10 minutes.

FA_{0.9}Cs_{0.1}PbI₃ material preparation

The 1M FA_{0.9}Cs_{0.1}PbI₃ perovskite films were deposited from a precursor solution prepared by dissolving 0.9 mmol of FAI, 0.1 mmol of CsI, and 1 mmol of PbI₂ in 1 ml of a mixed solvent consisting of DMF and DMSO in a 4:1 ratio. This precursor solution was continuously stirred at 60 °C for 1 hour and then left to stir overnight. The resulting perovskite solution was then spin-coated onto the substrate, first at 1000 rpm for 10 seconds, followed by 5000 rpm for 30 seconds. During the second spin-coating step, 200 μL of ethyl acetate was dropped onto the spinning substrate 5 seconds before the end. Finally, the samples were annealed at 100 °C for 15 minutes. All fabrication steps were performed in a nitrogen-filled glovebox.

CH₃NH₃PbI₃ material preparation

Samples MAPI A and MAPI B were fabricated from precursor solutions containing 1mmol of PbI₂ and 1 mmol of CH₃NH₃I dissolved, in 1 ml of DMF. Different amount of MACl (2.5 wt% for MAPI A and 1.5 wt% for MAPI B) were added to these solutions. After stirring overnight, the solutions were spin-coated onto glass substrates at 4500 rpm for 40 seconds. The resulting films were then annealed at 100 °C for 3 minutes to create the CH₃NH₃PbI₃ ·MACl layers. Once cooled to room temperature, the films were briefly exposed to CH₃NH₂ gas for about 2 seconds. After the gas was released from the films, the films were subjected to a final annealing at 150 °C for 10 minutes to produce high-quality CH₃NH₃PbI₃ films. All the steps were performed in a nitrogen-filled glovebox. More details can be found in publication [3]

Sample MAPI C was deposited on corning glass substrates from a precursor solution performed by dissolving 1.5 mmol PbI₂ and 1.5 mmol MAI in 1.5 ml solvent mixture of GBL and DMSO in a ratio of 3:2. This mixture was continuously stirred at 60 °C. The resulting perovskite solution was then spin-coated onto the substrate, first at 1000 rpm for 10 seconds and then at 5000 rpm for 30 seconds. During the second spin-coating step, 150 µL of chlorobenzene was dropped onto the spinning substrate 5 seconds before the end. Finally, the samples were annealed at 100 °C for 10 minutes. All the steps were performed in a nitrogen-filled glovebox.

Photothermal Deflection Spectroscopy measurements

The Photothermal Deflection Spectroscopy measurements were performed by a home-made setup equipped with 150W Xe lamp and Andor Kymera 328i. Slits were set to 1 mm. Focusing optics with magnification 1:1 was used. Combination of grating number of grooves and slit widths gave theoretical resolution $\Delta E/E \approx 0.01$, where E was photon energy. Real resolution, according to spectral linewidth measurements, was $\Delta E/E \leq 0.02$. As a thermal sensitive liquid, Flutec PP1 was used. Refractive index was 1.25. Simultaneously, transmittance and reflectance were measured by integration spheres in front and behind the cuvette (not directly in front or behind the sample), cuvette internal dimensions were 10 x10 mm. Absorptance from PDS effect was absolutely scaled according to $1 - R - T$ measured by integrating spheres. Absorption coefficient was then evaluated from absorptance/transmittance ratio from a smooth sample on glass according to equations from ref. [4]. For other purposes of absorptance comparison the simple equation is assumed to be $A \cong 1 - \exp(-\alpha\delta d)$. More accurately, the equation reads $A_{exp} \cong (1 - R_0) [1 - \exp(-\alpha\delta d_{exp})]$, where R_0 is the reflectance on the first surface, d_{exp} is actual thin-film thickness. In high absorption region, the R_0 reflectance equal to the experimentally observed reflectance of the real stack, but for the purposes of this study we assume $R_0 \cong R$ everywhere. From experimentally obtained A_{exp} we calculated absorptance A that is corrected to reflectance effects and corrected to thickness variations as $A \cong 1 - \exp [d/d_{exp} * \ln(1 - A_0/(1 - R))]$.

Figure S2: Absorption coefficient and refractive index of MAPI perovskite layer obtained from PDS measurement and numeric fitting procedure.

Fourier Transform Photocurrent Spectroscopy measurements

On the samples dedicated for FTPS measurements, the planar electrodes were prepared by evaporation gold through mechanical mask. The contact distance is 0.5 mm. The electrode pattern is in Figure S2.

Figure S3: electrode pattern for FTPS measurements.

Figure S4: Sketch of the FTPS sample arrangement and the effect of the illumination direction and the role of trapped light. In the case of glass side the long travelling photons contribute more to the measurement.

FTPS was performed by FTIR Thermo Nicolet 8700 equipped with external tungsten light source and external voltage source and pre-amplifier Keithley 428. Voltage bias 10 V was applied, giving DC current in the range of ~ 10 nA. Preamplification 10^8 V/A was applied. Infrared glass optical filter RG 780 from Thorlabs was used to suppress visible part of the spectrum and to collect sub-bandgap part of the spectrum. Scan speed velocity was 0.16 cm/s leading to modulation frequency around 4 kHz. Frequency dependence was corrected based on the measurements at twice and three times higher modulation frequencies.

Scanning Electron Microscopy measurements

The thicknesses of the perovskite thin films were determined from sample cross sections using scanning electron microscope MAIA 3, TESCAN at voltage of 5 kV.

Figure S5: SEM images of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ samples.

Atomic Force Microscopy

Surface roughness was measured by AFM using WiTec alpha300 SNOM system utilizing non-contact AFM method with Si probes. Measured sample area was $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$.

RMS= 51 ± 8 nm

S 160 (int. no. 2024 23a)

0 nm

RMS= 72 ± 17 nm

M 160 (int. no. 2025 I3)

0 nm

RMS= 67 ± 13 nm

L 160 (int. no. 2025 C3)

RMS=125 ± 19 nm
S 250 (int. no. 2025 G3)

RMS=105 ± 23 nm
M 250 (int. no. 2025 B2)

RMS=210 ± 40 nm
L 250 (int. no. 2025 A2)

RMS=210 ± 70 nm
S 500 (int. no. 2024 C2)

RMS=390 ± 60 nm
M 500 (int. no. 2025 D15)

RMS=63 ± 14 nm
L 500 (int. no. 2024 E1)

Figure S6: Morphology of native roughness of MAPI samples.

ZnO A, RMS = 26 ± 6 nm

ZnO A with Au, RMS = 26 ± 6 nm

ZnO B, RMS = 34 ± 10 nm

ZnO B with Au, RMS = 32 ± 9 nm

ZnO C, RMS = 50 ± 17 nm

ZnO C with Au, RMS = 61 ± 17 nm

FTO, RMS = 173 ± 42 nm

FTO with Au, RMS = 150 ± 50 nm

Figure S7: Morphology of nano-rough TCO substrates before (left image) and after (right image) the deposition of gold layer.

glass reference, $\text{RMS} = 8 \pm 2 \text{ nm}$

glass reference with Au $10 \pm 2 \text{ nm}$

glass A, $\text{RMS} = 112 \pm 21 \text{ nm}$

glass A with Au, $\text{RMS} = 266 \pm 53 \text{ nm}$

glass B, $\text{RMS} = 80 \pm 21 \text{ nm}$

glass B with Au, $\text{RMS} = 57 \pm 13 \text{ nm}$

glass F, $\text{RMS} = 220 \pm 110 \text{ nm}$

glass F with Au, $\text{RMS} = 500 \pm 100 \text{ nm}$

Figure S8: Morphology of micro-rough glass substrates before (left image) and after (right image) the deposition of gold layer.

Angular Distribution Function measurements

Figure S9: Angular distribution function measurement setup.

The measurement of Angular distribution function (ADF) consisted of a setup at Figure S3. Pinhole #1 was used for removing the scattered part of the laser, pinhole #2 was used for removing the diffraction pattern from pinhole #1. Adjustable table was used to direct the specular part of the reflection back into the pinhole, so that there was only the scattered part of the reflectance on the screen. Note that if the specularly reflected beam is falling on the screen, it will produce strongly disturbing halo effect on the resulting picture. This absolutely has to be prevented. For the purposes of measurement of the laser energy, the adjustable table was readjusted to direct the specular part into energy meter. Pinhole #3 plus black paper was there to trap all the transmitted beam. Distance between the sample and the screen was 10 cm. DSLR camera with CMOS chip was used to take pictures at ISO 800 and different exposure times ranging from around 0.1 s to 1 s. Pictures were stored in raw DNG format. Picture intensity along a straight radial line was first extracted by ImageJ software and then corrected for exposure time and for saturation effect by following equation (L_{true} is the corrected intensity in relative numbers, L_{exp} is the extracted value, and *exposure time* is the time of the camera shutter):

$$L_{true} = \frac{-\ln(1 - L_{exp}/75)}{\text{exposure time}}$$

The resulting set of curves for different exposure times were fitted in the region of their common overlap by polynomials and recalculated from pixel positions into angles by arctg function.

References

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